

attained more than 80% germination.

Under ambient conditions, the coarse and semifine grain varieties broke their dormancy rapidly (56–63 d) compared to superfine grain Basmati 370 and Punjab Basmati I (132–140 d) (Table 1). The fine grain varieties that matured and were harvested under low temperatures broke dormancy slowly; the coarse and semifine grain varieties that encountered slightly higher temperatures during maturation and harvest lost their dormancy rapidly. It appears that temperature fluctuations near full maturity and at harvest contributed quantitatively to the dormancy barriers.

To break dormancy, we presoaked seeds in GA₃, KNO₃, and water at 25°C for 24 h and applied a heat treatment at 50°C in the oven for 24, 48, 72, and 96 h.

Water soaking showed negligible results (Table 2), indicating that dormancy barriers are not leachable. Presoaking seeds in GA₃ (500 µg/ml) or KNO₃ (500 µl/ml) broke dormancy in all varieties. Heat treatment at 50°C for 96 h was most effective in breaking dormancy. The treatments which broke the dormancy appeared to act at the hull level by inhibiting O₂ absorbing systems and at the embryo level by enhancing O₂ availability and removing inhibitors. A two-block hypothesis is posited: one block seems to be at the husk level and one at the embryo level. □

Table 1. Germination of rice varieties during postharvest storage under ambient conditions. Ludhiana, India.

Variety	Germination (%) at indicated days after harvest (DH)										Dormancy (d)	
	<i>Coarse and semifine grain</i>											
	0	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63		
	DH											
PR106	36	40	45	48	56	68	72	76	79	86	56-63	
IR8	24	30	38	44	55	64	68	72	78	82	56-63	
Jaya	24	28	32	40	47	54	62	69	76	90	56-63	
PR4141	58	60	64	67	70	73	75	78	80	88	56-63	
	<i>Superfine grain</i>											
	0	7	63	70	98	105	112	119	125	132	140	
	DH											
Punjab Basmati 1	2	5	15	20	28	33	38	45	63	75	85	132-140
Bas 370	–	2	5	12	20	42	60	75	75	88	92	132-140

Table 2. Treatments to break dormancy and enhance germination. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Germination (%)					
	PR106	IR8	Jaya	PR 4141	Pb Bas 1	Bas370
Control (initial germination)	36.6	24.3	24.3	50.6	2.0	–
Water soaking (24 h)	38.6	32.3	30.0	60.0	7.6	8.3
GA ₃ soaking (24 h)						
100 µg/ml	57.3	52.0	53.3	69.0	54.6	50.6
200 µg/ml	71.6	72.0	68.3	77.6	70.6	63.0
500 µg/ml	86.0	83.3	91.3	95.6	85.6	87.3
KNO ₃ soaking (24 h)						
100 µg/ml	43.3	37.3	40.0	59.3	11.3	10.3
200 µg/ml	65.6	58.0	59.6	71.0	46.0	39.3
500 µg/ml	81.0	80.3	80.6	81.0	76.6	71.6
Heat treatment (50°C)						
24 h	55.0	52.3	61.0	64.6	36.0	23.3
48 h	70.3	68.3	76.3	77.0	49.0	47.6
72 h	81.0	79.3	84.0	89.0	67.3	70.6
96 h	93.0	92.6	94.3	92.0	81.3	80.0
LSD P = 0.05	6.3	6.5	6.4	5.0	7.7	5.8

Inheritance of tillering ability in three crosses of upland varieties

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Tiller number at 40 d after seeding (DAS) is indicative of the early growth vigor essential to an early-maturing genotype. We studied allelic relationships, estimates of heritability, and residual heterosis for number of tillers at 40 DAS in 3 F₂ populations of crosses with upland rice varieties that included traditional Abdoulaye Mano, and Barafita from Senegal.

In all F₂ populations, heritability

Means, ranges, mean square, heritability coefficients, and residual heterosis for number of tillers in the F₂ of 3 crosses. ISRA, Senegal.

Population	Observations (no.)	Mean	Range	Mean square	Heritability coefficient (H)	Residual heterosis
IR12624-65-2	30	6.70	2–13	7.87		
IRAT144	28	3.14	1– 8	4.27		
F ₂	160	6.11	1–19	13.69	57.68%	–4.32
IRAT144	50	4.14	1–10	9.87		
Abdoulaye Mano	52	4.83	1–15	32.69		
F ₂	160	5.50	1–16	40.39	55.54%	–18.45
IRAT144	52	4.80	1– 9	5.33		
Barafita	52	5.57	1–11	8.45		
F ₂	160	5.52	1–24	19.58	65.73%	–6.50

exceeded 50% for the character studied. In the IR12624-65-2/IRAT144 F₂, more plants showed tiller numbers closer to the IR12624-65-2 parent, which has the

higher tillering potential, than to the IRAT144 parent (see table). The distribution of F₂ plants was bimodal (see figure). Adjusting observed data to

Distribution of numbers of tillers 40 DAS in the F₂ of 3 crosses of upland varieties. ISRA, Senegal.

the theoretical level for 1 gene segregation (75–25%) gives a highly significant χ^2 .

In IRAT144/Abdoulaye Mano, environmental variance undoubtedly contributed to the continuous variation in the F₂ plants, which corresponds to

parental values. The weak expression of the tiller number character seems to influence moderate tiller numbers most. This explains why the residual heterosis was negative.

In the IRAT144/Barafita F₂, tiller

numbers at 40 DAS varied continuously. Data could not be used to test goodness of fit with expected segregation ratio. The distribution skewed more toward higher tiller numbers than it did in Barafita. □

Performance of ORS26-2014-4 (Lalat), a medium-duration variety

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ORS26-2014-4 (Obs 677/IR2071 //Bikram/ W1263), popularly called Lalat, is a 135-d variety. We compared it with 23 promising rice cultures of similar duration. The trial had 30-d-old seedlings transplanted 20 Feb 1986 at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 6.5-m² plots, in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Fertilizer was 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Pest infestation was measured at peak incidence.

Lalat performed best with a yield of 4.3 t/ha (see table). Its grain is medium bold with white kernel. The plant was 85.3 cm tall, flowered in 97 d, and produced 276 panicles/m². It was resistant to caseworm, leaffolder, and stem borer at heading. □

Yield performance and reactions to insect pests of 24 promising rice cultures. Chiplima, Sambalpur, India, 1986.

Culture	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles/m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)	Caseworm damage ^a	Leaffolder damage ^a (%)	Whitehead damage ^a (%)
ORI58-7-1	99.5	99	238.7	1.8	1.7	11.2	11.1
ORI96-2	74.7	99	345.0	2.1	0.7	7.5	7.5
OR131-5-8	84.0	92	292.0	1.2	0.3	15.3	15.3
NDU80	96.7	97	270.3	2.4	1.7	11.0	11.0
RP1570-6-5-4-1	88.8	95	211.0	1.5	0.3	13.3	13.3
KM6	78.0	88	257.7	1.8	0.7	15.7	15.1
UPR79-123	85.5	95	236.3	1.5	1.3	11.7	11.7
UPR103-44-2	81.3	101	232.3	1.7	4.3	12.5	12.5
OR268-408-5	87.8	110	202.7	1.2	1.3	8.9	8.8
NDR302	92.7	99	310.3	1.9	1.7	11.2	10.0
RP1570-44-1	87.3	95	306.0	2.3	0.3	13.2	13.2
RP1699-174-97-1	99.0	97	236.7	1.8	0.3	15.1	15.1
RP1699-183-133-1	97.2	106	326.0	1.3	0.3	11.0	11.2
RP1699-26-1-1	94.3	104	348.3	1.9	0.7	14.6	14.6
UPR231-28-1-2	80.3	91	290.3	2.5	1.3	11.7	11.7
RP2151-40-1	90.0	102	338.3	3.7	1.7	8.2	8.2
RP2151-21-22	96.5	103	295.0	3.0	0.7	5.8	5.8
RP1832-23-3-4	74.5	88	296.0	1.5	0.3	13.5	13.5
IR18348-36-3-3	89.3	92	255.3	2.4	0.7	10.7	10.7
Rasi	83.5	90	225.0	2.1	1.3	14.4	11.1
IR36	78.0	90	229.0	2.0	0.3	10.3	10.0
RP2240-153-1-51	79.0	92	215.7	2.1	0.7	14.6	14.5
ORS26-2014-4 (Lalat)	85.3	97	275.7	4.3	0.3	9.9	9.9
ORS26-2008	87.0	99	265.3	2.2	0.7	10.9	10.9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.